

Contextualism and rupture. Modernism in the Post-war reconstruction of Lübeck

Introduction

The debate over the reconstruction of bombed German cities, which started still during the war years, was based on two antagonistic principles - Wiederaufbau & Neubeginn - the rebuilding of the old cities & a radical modernization of the city structure based on tabula rasa. This was the main point of confrontation between traditionalist² and modernist³ architects. Plans for decentralization and functional zoning of major German cities started to be discussed already in the 1920's (Durth & Gutschow, 1987), aiming at providing better qualities to the cities' built environment. Therefore, the large scale destruction brought about by WWII was seen by many planners and architects as an opportunity to put in practice the 1920-30's planning concepts and as a chance to rebuild the cities according to the doctrine of Modernism. In 1945, Paul Baumgarten overlooking the Brandenburger Tor in Berlin, declared: "I radiate: what an opportunity to plan a new urban landscape here and what a chance to pull down the ruins and to build new modern buildings".⁴ Drieschner (2000)

In general, in the post-war reconstruction in South Germany, traditionalism in architecture and town planning was more influential. In East Germany, this conflict did not develop much further because of the strict rules coming from Moscow where Stalin imposed the Socialist Realism architecture based on a monu-

mental new traditionalism combining pseudo neo-classicism (Stalin Allee, in East Berlin) or new-Gothic (Lange Strasse, in Rostock). During the Stalin years, the so-called Stalinist Architecture (Tarchanov & Kawtaradse: 1992), was the ideological response to the International Modernism, seen as a symbol of the western decadence and capitalism. In North Germany, Modernism was to express the principles and qualities put forward by the *Interbau Berlin 1957*, illustrated by many post-war architectural developments such as in Wolfsburg, Kiel, Hamburg among others.

There were 4 basic planning and architectural policies underlying the reconstruction of German cities:

Reconstruction in Germany ≈ 1950-60	single buildings	building ensembles	Examples in East Germany
historic reconstruction : - "Total Rebuilding"	Zeughaus, Braunschweig St. Michaelis, Hamburg (as an example among many destroyed churches)	Prinzipalmarkt, Münster Böttgerstrasse, Bremen Siedl. Dulsberg, Hamburg	Rathaus, Leipzig Oper, Berlin (East) Steintor, Rostock
historic reconstruction allowing some changes and new additions: - "Partial Adaptation"	Paulskirche, Frankfurt Alte Pinakothek, München St. Martin-Kirche, Kassel	Römerberg, Frankfurt City Center of Fulda City Center of Nürnberg City Center Freudenstadt Martinsviertel, Köln	Messehof, Leipzig Neuer Markt (south), Rostock
reconstruction with changes and/or new building types: - "Alteration"	Schloss, Kiel Rathaus, Stuttgart Maxburg, München	Marktplatz, Stuttgart City Center, Braunschweig g City Center, Hannover	City Center of Neubrandenburg Alter Markt, Magdeburg Krämerstrasse, Rostock
rebuilding according to a entirely new architectural and urban framework: - "Rupture"	Liederhalle, Stuttgart Gedächtniskirche, Berlin Haus der Bürgerschaft, Bremen	Treppenstrasse, Kassel Grindelberg, Hamburg Hansaviertel, Berlin Neckarufer, Heilbronn Helgoland	Stalinallee, Berlin (East) Alexanderplatz, Berlin (East) Fischerinsel, Berlin (East) Lange Strasse, Rostock

Table 1

Lübeck

In 1942, the British Air Force squadron flew a heavy air raid on Lübeck. This was the first large-scale systematic bombing of a German city directed to the civil population as a means to weaken the war resistance during WWII, as used by Hitler's terror technique in Guernica, Spain, and Coventry, England. During three hours, 140 tons of bombs were thrown over Lübeck destroying 1/5 of the entire city centre, 1400 buildings, including: the *Gründungsviertel* or the Hanseatic building fabric former inhabited by the rich merchants, the *Dombezirk* (Fig.1), a residential area around the cathedral, the east part of the city inhabited by handworkers, the churches of St. Marien and St. Petri, leaving 300 dead and 1000 wounded. In many cases, the heavy damage inflicted upon the city, left only building facades and walls which for security reasons had to be demolished.

The planning for the reconstruction of the devastated city of Lübeck (Fig.2) started immediately after the air attack of 1942 (Pieper: 1946) being regarded as a guideline for other German cities. Even Heinrich Tessenow, later participated in this process. Although different in concepts, these plans dealt with the city's urgent needs such as infrastructure, traffic improvement and the basic qualities of urban space embodied in Modernism, such as "light, air, sun", and put forward the clearing of bombed areas, the widening of old streets and the redesign of the block structures, plot subdivisions and building arrangements within large inner courtyards.

Fig. 1 – Bombing raids over Lübeck in 1942 showing the damaged Cathedral (Dom) on the left side.
Source: German Military Archives.

Fig. 2 – Plan of the historic center of Lübeck with the damaged areas resulting from the bombing raids from 28./29. March 1942
zerstört = totally destroyed
beschädigt = partially destroyed areas
Examples discussed in this paper:
1 - Krähenstrasse
2 - Merchants Quarter
3 - Schmiedestrasse
Source: (Beyme: 1992)

In post-war Germany, public discussions between Traditionalism and Modernism took place among architects and planners all over the country. In Lübeck, Modernism was taken as the major urban and architectural concept and it was followed by a strong citizens' reaction and criticism due to the first post-war interventions in the old city spelling out Modern architectural vocabulary - Rathausmarkt (Fig.3) and Breite Strasse - using contemporary design and materials (concret, glass and ceramic), and in some cases mixed with unplastered red bricks. Although Modernism was the main factor underlying the post-war reconstruction of Lübeck's centre (the so-called Gothic town constructed in brick), the resulting built forms show contrasting approaches and attitudes to the problem of fitting new building structures into its historic townscape, as illustrated by some of the three examples here discussed, such as Krähenstrasse, the former *Gründerviertel* (the Merchant's quarter, consisted of Fischstrasse, Alfstrasse and Mengstrasse) and Schmiedestrasse.

Fig. 3 – A detail of the listed buildings comprising the Rathaus ensemble. On the left side, the new building addition spelling out Modernism, an intervention from 1955 by architect Horenburg. On the right side, a detail of the old Rathaus' Renaissance facade.
Foto: klaus brendle

The insertion of new building structures into the outstanding old physical and spatial structure of Lübeck was not an easy task in the post-war reconstruction as Modernist urbanism tenets established by the Athens Charter took barely into account the cities' pre-existing built environment. Therefore, Modernism has been strongly criticized as causing further severe losses to the old European city centres, or according to Zahn⁵ (1999: 25), even destroying their cultural heritage in order to build a

new urban and architectural order. As stated by Kostof (1992), post-war urban renewal, "seemed to finish the work of the bombs".

How to harmonise the city's new and old fabric and to integrate them into a homogeneous urban context without neglecting its historic ambience, character and without re-producing replicas, repetition or pastiches and even historicist references not tolerated by Modernism?

Modernism took a polemic path in the post-war reconstruction of Lübeck, where the integration of modern buildings into its old urban context did not always take into account the *strict* preservation of the city's morphological pattern. Rather, design solutions favoured changes in its urban block structures, plot subdivisions and the building arrangements within them, bringing about a break with the previous dominant urban tissue.

These changes primarily consisted of new block configurations where the narrow plots were to accommodate new continuous building schemes parallel to the street frontages. Furthermore, the dominant vertical line of the facades with its characteristic pitched roofs and tall gabled houses of the Middle Ages were replaced by new buildings structures with marked horizontality which shaped a completely new streetscape although keeping or adapting some basic elements of Modernism in North Germany such as *flachgeneigte Dächer* (gentle inclined roofs), red bricks, white window frames, etc. (Fig.4).

Fig. 4 – Kohlmarkt / Rathausmarkt Lübeck (in the background the old Rathaus and St. Marien)
Foto: klaus brendle

It can be argued that, **contextualism** was the underlying principle of most of the early Modernist post-war reconstruction of Lübeck, as expressed in the great concern with the new buildings height, size,

scale, bulk, massing, materials and design which intended to avoid a stark contrast with the neighbouring pre-existing building ensembles, thus granting a minimal impact upon the historic built environment, with emphasis to the city's skyline dominated by the 7 churches towers of its magnificent medieval temples. On the other hand, even the **deliberate contrast** of the new building structures erected on Schmiedestrasse, whose urban concept refused to restore the area to its earlier conditions shows no indifference to the old city, while established a clear rupture with its traditional building forms.

Krähenstrasse

On Krähenstrasse, the street line was rectified and widened and the building lines set back at the expense of further demolition of living urban tissue in order to establish a direct and better traffic connection with Wahnstrasse which became an important east-west axis in the city's road structure (Fig.5). As in other interventions in the city, the block structure and the narrow plot subdivision were replaced by a continuous street frontage with a remarked horizontality whose building heights and pitched roofs kept in with the surroundings. The buildings display new typological elements such as balconies running along the facades, some of which in curved lines, and a rich variety of wall cladding materials, colours and particular design composition for the shopfronts, some of which are still preserved.

Fig. 5 – Krähenstrasse. On the right side, the postwar reconstruction architectural developments.
Foto: klaus brendle

The Merchants Quarter: Fischstrasse, Alfstrasse and Mengstrasse

Distinct approaches and design solutions were used in the rebuilding of the Merchants quarter (Fig.6), although there was a clear intention to respect its surrounding built environment and the overwhelming presence of the Marienkirche (»1200), one of the most significant examples of Gothic architecture in elaborate brickwork in Northern Europe. On Schlüsselbuden, the block facing the Marienkirche shows a contextualism without imitative mimesis, rather with a close association or symbiosis with the

surrounding built form. An intervention which established a historical reference with Lübeck's local architecture and managed an environmental integration within it without renouncing to the contemporary architectural idiom of Modernism, its materials and techniques. These buildings shows a free typological re-interpretation of the area's former architecture as seen in its pitched roofs and in its facade composition blending in stones, concrete, glass and structural elements.

Fig. 6 – Contemporary airview of the Merchants Quarter (Gründerviertel). On the left side between the churches of St. Marien and St. Petri.
Source: Photo by H.Weitzel.

The design of the new dwellings and public schools in Fischstrasse, Alfstrasse and Mengstrasse seemed to reject historic references to the previous urban fabric by replacing the narrow plot patterns and the rich variety of the building heights by uniform rows of buildings shaping a monolithic and continuous street frontage with a remarked horizontality. New architectural elements (galleries) and materials (concrete, coloured ceramic, decorative panels, glass walls, etc.) were introduced in the buildings of the *Dorothea-Schlözer Schule* and the *Hanse Schule für Wirtschaft und Verwaltung*, however their design qualities proved to be very modest⁶. The Merchants quarter greatly lost its essential previous urban and architectural character. However, the new erected buildings⁷ show a particular architectural merit, in using the modernist architectural language. On the other hand, the design concept did not ignore the former urban spatial structure of the area as it was carried out in Kassel or Heilbronn - although inserting new building types, by using a number of prominent gabled facades, thus creating a new cityscape.

Schmiedestrasse

Schmiedestrasse is regarded as the most destructive post-war intervention in the old city of Lübeck. An intentional contrast with the surroundings, the buildings on Schmiedestrasse were devised from the outset to be Modern. An unambiguous design choice avoiding historicist references and supplanting the double-coding combining modern and traditional regional architectural languages. A wholesale development consisting of free-standing buildings

which radically differed from Lübeck's tall, narrow, street-oriented row houses of the Middle Ages by rejecting the traditional building frontages and inserting on its urban tissue new block structures and single buildings spelling out contemporary forms.

On St. Petri Kirche's adjacent area (Fig.7), the old curving street line generating irregular blocks and an organic pattern was widened. An urban operation that had been planned since 1942, as a means to improve the congested traffic system in Lübeck central area.

Fig. 7 – Urban space analysis of Schmiedestrasse
right - before the war
left - postwar reconstruction
above - elements of cityscape
below - spatial structure of space and visual elements
Source: Sketch by klaus brendle

The urban and architectural design concept rejected any accommodation to existing typologies and local building traditions but it shows some regards to the area's urban scale by establishing a height limit for the new structures, although greatly altering the old urban pattern by modifying the former street line with single building units freely arranged into the building plots.

The new buildings types and spatial organization reflected a concern with exploring the new technical possibilities of the reinforced concrete as well as their aesthetical design qualities. It is interesting to note that the three main large buildings on Schmiedestrasse (the *Parkhaus Mitte*, the *Gesundheitsamt* and the *Schwimmhalle*) made reference to Lübeck's traditional red bricks on their facades but devoid of any stylistic mimesis. The *Parkhaus Mitte*,

a large three-storey building mixing concrete and glass ribbon windows established a high visual impact with its surroundings dominated by the outstanding structure of St. Petri Kirche (Fig.8), while introduced a half-round element which greatly altered the pre-existing surroundings, although making reference to the curved street line. The *Schwimmhalle* is also a massive structure inserted on an entire block which shows a planned distinction with the pre-existing building arrangements, spatial organization, proportions and scale.

Fig. 8 – New buildings on Schmiedestrasse, with St.Petri Church on the background
Photo: M.Brix 1975

On the other side of the road, new constructions such as the Rieckmann shop building searched to harmonise with the roof line of a restored department store from the 1930s (a typical elaborate brickwork of North Germany) which closes the street at Klingenberg Platz without making reference to the steep angle of the typical tiled roofs so common in other post-war developments in Lübeck. The Rieckmann building introduced new typological elements such as balconies and undecorated concrete window frames.

On Schmiedestrasse, the historic continuity of the city was understood as the city's building process itself. A typological contrast with respect to building forms, techniques and materials but which allowed Modern structures to be fitted into the old town. The most conservative and radical conservationists took Schmiedestrasse as a disruptive or intrusive intervention in the old town. However, it is important to understand that there, Modernism was bringing new spatial organizations, forms, ambiances and strongly rejected to practise the stylistic *pastiche* and urban cosmetic and dared to establish a honest dialogue with past.

It can be argued that in many ways, the intervention in Schmiedestrasse was also **responsive** to the

city's historic character considering that it did not develop freely as in the *Papageien-Siedlung* by Ernst May or the building of the former *National Versicherungs-Gesellschaften* (Fig.9), both in Lübeck periphery, where there was less historic or environmental restrictions.

Fig. 9 – Air view of the *National Versicherungs-Gesellschaften* headquarter, on Travemünder Allee, Lübeck.
Source: Verkehrsamt der Hansestadt Lübeck, 1967-68.

Final Remarks

Although carried out according to distinct approaches, the examples discussed above sought to grant the preservation of the city's old urban scenography in keeping with its historic ambience. These interventions leave no doubt about the **contextual** response to the historical continuity of the city, which without making a simplistic reproduction, replaced the old built forms by new ones with references to the pre-existing built environment.

In Krähenstrasse the street pattern was changed in order to comply with the city's requirement for modernization such as traffic and infrastructure, and although the buildings erected made clear references in respect to the surrounding historic ambience, they were not just a copy of the old. On the opposite: by exploring the new materials possibilities which concret could offer, the design concept incorporated aesthetics qualities from the 50's and 60's being modern and contemporary. Thus, rejecting the anachronic trend to decorativism and historicism and the easy stylistic concessions to the past which were largely used in the design of many buildings in Germany, such as lintels, windows frames, cornices and so on.

In Alfstrasse and Fischstrasse, the new inserted building structures brought about changes to the old plot configuration. For the new function introduced in the area, (eg. the two new schools: *Dorothea-Schlözer Schule* and the *Hanse Schule für Wirtschaft und Verwaltung*), new building types were designed. The streetline was kept but the streets were widened, although partially keeping its old structure and some building qualities of the past such as the brick facades typical of North German Mod-

ernism. The new ensemble features are clearly recognisable as a post-war intervention which combines contemporary urban and architectural approaches with a great regard with the area historical background.

In Schmiedestrassen, the new buildings are clearly the result of a cubic composition of pure volumes with geometrical forms and the functionalist design of Modernism. New materials and techniques generating new design alternatives with no reference to tradition, establishing a clear rupture with past building arrangements and typologies, etc., but fitting into the old surroundings (Fig.10). It is striking the sharp contrast between St. Petri Kirche and the clear horizontal structure of the flat-roof and curved glass facade of the *Parkhaus Mitte*, but it is also relevant to stress the concern with the building heights, where the absence of high-rise constructions allowed the preservation of the area's urban scale and character.

Fig. 10 – Contemporary airview of the Hansestadt Lübeck. In the middle, the Church of St.Petri and the Schmiedestrassen with *Parkhaus*, *Gesundheitsamt* and *Schwimmhalle*. Source: Verlag Schöning & Co.

As shown in Table 2, some of the leading principles underlying the post-war reconstruction in Germany (Table 1), are also found in the reshaping of Lübeck central area:

Reconstruction in Lübeck ≈ 1950-60's	single buildings	building ensembles
historic reconstruction : -“Total Rebuilding”	St.Marien St.Petri	-
historic reconstruction allowing some changes and new additions: -“ Partial Adaptation”	Buddenbrock-Haus Dorn	Mühlenstrasse (infills) Sandstrasse Königstrasse (infills)
reconstruction with changes and/ or new building types: -“Alteration”	Dorn-Gemeindehaus Rathaus-Hof	Krähenstrasse Breite Strasse Holstenstrasse Rathaus-Markt
rebuilding according to a complete new architectural and urban framework: - “Rupture”	Haerder-Building BfG-Bank Schwimmhalle Parkhaus Mitte Landesbank Anny Friede Building	Fisch-/Alf-/Mengstrasse (Merchant Quarter) Schmiedestrassen Beckergube

Table 2

The post-war interventions of Lübeck examined in this paper display a number of elements of the Modern architectural vocabulary and principles, such as:

- cubic, geometrical pure forms
- accentuated horizontality
- plain facades
- functional building arrangements
- visible constructive elements.

In addition, it can also be found elements of the early North-German Modernism:

- *Backsteinarchitektur* (brick architecture)
- saddle roofs (maximum 30% inclination, ceramic tiles and short eaves)
- row of windows
- contrasting red brickwork, light plaster or concrete elements and white window frames.

And, particular features of the 1950-60's Modernism in Germany such as:

- the use of ornaments such as steel balustrades (stairs, balconies, windows, etc.)
- the use of lively/colourful/bright panels, reliefs, friezes in ceramic and bricks, among other materials
- larger, rowed windows in walls which have no massive character.

Furthermore, it indicates that the historic built environment of Lübeck was taken into account in the architectural design and postures:

- avoiding flat roofs, large scales and curtain walls
- careful use of steel and glass elements, transparency
- keeping somehow the historical street patterns
- using bricks (unplastered).

These examples of the post-war reconstruction of Lübeck brings a contribution to city building as it demystifies the so-called “history denial” of Modernism and its impossibility to put together old and new building forms. Its **contextualism** is illustrated in the dialogue with history, which must not be confused with the symplistic and picturesque recreation of figurative elements. Rather, is responsive to the urban and spacial pre-existing city structure, contemporary and without reproducing old building types (Fig.11).

Unfortunately, these buildings have been considered as potential areas for further redevelopments in the city centre and their demolition have even being proposed by local politicians and architects. ‘*Architekten-Idee: Haerder weg, Parkhaus weg*’ - was the headline of an article published in a local newspaper⁸, calling for the demolition of some of these post-war building ensembles to make way for new shopping centres.

Fig. 11 – Plan of the postwar reconstruction of Lübeck from 1957 by the *Bauverwaltung / Planungsamt* (building administration / planning office). The three areas discussed in this paper are highlighted. Source: (Beyme: 1992)

It is interesting to emphasize that the Rathaus-Hof (Fig.3), one of the buildings comprising the Rathaus Markt as developed in the 50's, is a listed building, revealing some regards from the Lübeck Conservation Authority with its post-war Modernism. The old Hanseatic centre, has been since 1978, part of the Unesco World Heritage. However, architectural and urban history in Lübeck does not end with the Hanseatic or XIX century periods. It is time to carry out a comprehensive evaluation of the still intact post-war building ensembles of Lübeck designed according to Modernism, their qualities and the extent to which they integrate in the old city fabric. Should the last 50 years of Lübeck architectural and urban developments not be considered as history too? And the *Wiederaufbau*, the reconstruction of Lübeck not to be seen as a genuine part of the Hanseatic city?

NOTES

¹ In collaboration with Maria de Betânia Uchôa Cavalcanti-Brendle.

² This refers to the German traditionalism in architecture as developed before WWII

(Muthesius, Tessenow, Bonatz, Schmitthener, among others), and not to the vernacular

architecture adopted by the Nazis during the III Reich.

³ (Gropius, Gutschow, Hillebrecht, Meyer, Reichow, Scharoun, etc.)

⁴ "Ich strahlte: Welch eine Möglichkeit, hier eine neue

Landschaft zu planen, und welche eine Möglichkeit, das Ruinenfeld abzutragen und neue moderne Häuser zu bauen".

⁵ Bausenator Volker Zahn - Head of *Stadtplanung und Bau* in Lübeck since 1991.

⁶ According to Schwarz (1981) and Steffann (1980), this was in line with one of the underlying principles of the early post-war reconstruction in Germany.

⁷ Designed by Dietz-Brandt (Göttingen) and by the *Hochbauamt Lübeck* (1954/1957).

⁸ Latzel (2000).

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Klaus Brendle. Diploma Engineer, Architect and City Planner with postgraduate studies in Architectural and Environmental Psychology and in Contemporary Design in Historic Built Environments. Lecturer in Architectural Psychology at Tübingen University, and in Townplanning and Architecture at Stuttgart University. Head of *planungsbuero architektur & anderes*, Lübeck, in charge with projects of urban renewal, interventions in old buildings and areas and design of urban spaces. Member of the SRL (*Vereinigung für Stadt-, Regional- und Landesplanung e.V.*) and BDA (*Bund Deutscher Architekten*).